

D8.2 Communication and Dissemination Plan

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MOIRAI

www.moirai-project.eu

Multiscale Ocean models and Information for climate Risk Assessment and Impact mitigation.

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Communication and Dissemination Plan

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DISSEMINATION LEVEL		
PU	Public, fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
Classified R-UE/EU-R	EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
Classified C-UE/EU-C	EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
Classified S-UE/EU-S	EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444	

DELIVERABLE TYPE		
R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	x
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	
DMP	Data management plan	
ETHICS	Deliverables related to ethics issues.	
SECURITY:	Deliverables related to security issues	
OTHER:	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.	

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

MOIRAI uncovers a comprehensive understanding of the ocean's dynamics and biogeochemical cycles through advanced models, integrating historical data, current observations, and future projections. It will significantly improve our understanding of climate change and advance our modelling capabilities towards regional, coastal, and biogeochemical climate models for European Seas. Not only this, but MOIRAI will improve prediction capabilities and provide for early-warning in support of preparedness and resilience.

MOIRAI modelling products will be integrated into digital twin frameworks such as digital twin of the ocean (DTO) and Destination Earth (DE). MOIRAI will also develop an original decision support tool called REASSHORE (Resilience and Adaptation Strategies Selection Hub for Ocean risks Assessment and End-users feedback), which will integrate with these existing and emerging technologies in providing basin-scale services.

The Communication and Dissemination (C&D) Plan lays out guidelines for maximising the visibility and impact of MOIRAI and its inherent activities. It outlines specific approaches towards C&D activities as they relate respectively to promotion of the project and to sharing results. Although not the main objective of the plan, this document also sets the groundwork for exploitation of MOIRAI outputs and products.

This plan describes the Tools and Channels that will be used, Target Groups, Key Messages, and defines Key Performance Indicators against which progress, and impact can be measured. Beginning with the creation of a visual identity (logo) that is easily identifiable and distinguishes MOIRAI from other projects or services, this plan will support the development of an excellent reputation for MOIRAI towards environmental management authorities, offshore industries such as fishing, aquaculture and renewable energies, the broader scientific community of climate and ocean modellers, the DTO/DE community, as well as various other stakeholders, end users, and the wider public.

The plan will be implemented from the outset of the project and monitored and updated throughout its duration. The C&D Plan will evolve during the lifespan of the project, in accordance with this process. A formal update will be presented as Deliverable 8.4 Communication and Dissemination Plan V2 by M42 (April 2028).

Acknowledgements:

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Introduction

1.1. Objectives of MOIRAI

MOIRAI, named after the three Greek goddesses of fate, stands as a pioneering project at the intersection of past, present, and future. MOIRAI weaves a comprehensive understanding of the ocean's dynamics and biogeochemical cycles through advanced models, integrating historical data, current observations, and future projections. Integrated into the frameworks of Destination Earth (DE) and the European Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO), MOIRAI will significantly advance our comprehension and mitigation of climate-related challenges.

The specific objectives are as follows:

1. Advance the representation and understanding of basin- and coastal- scale, ocean dynamics and biogeochemical cycle.
2. Build the capability to provide relevant ocean climate and risk services for different end-users, allowing for its replication in all SIX European seas.
3. Ensure MOIRAI model suite's interoperability with Destination Earth (DE) and European Digital Twin Ocean (European DTO) by deploying a new workflow management solution for i) reproducible modelling experimentation; ii) REASSHORE and its deployment in six use cases.
4. Build an interactive platform, REASSHORE, dedicated to two target groups: i) end-users (3 modules for the blue economy) and ii) policy-makers (a science-to-policy indicators dashboard) who will be trained on the hub during a dedicated workshop.
5. Perform life cycle costing and life-cycle assessment of MOIRAI's solutions deployment in each of the six use cases guaranteeing MOIRAI's sustainable approach.

Figure 1 - MOIRAI work package PERT chart.

The project is comprised of eight work packages (WP), as shown in Figure 1. WP1 deals with project management and coordination, WP2 works on refined climate and ocean physics models for regional seas, WP3 develops improved regional Biogeochemical (BGC) and ecosystem models for coastal services, WP4 develops multi-scale coastal models for impact and risk assessment, WP5 looks at model uncertainty quantification and high-performance computing (HPC) optimization, WP6 provides decision support tools, WP7 provides demonstrations, validation and feedback; and WP8 is dedicated to communication, dissemination, synergies and policy recommendations.

1.2. Objectives of the Communication and Dissemination Plan

The main objective of WP8 - Communication, Dissemination, Synergies and Policy Recommendations, is to raise the visibility of the project and the environmental challenges it aims to address. WP8, guided by a well-structured Communication and Dissemination Plan, will facilitate the promotion and sharing of project outcomes with scientific communities and end users. It will support engagement with stakeholders, including decision-makers, civil society, and other interested entities. This work package aims to encourage the uptake and utilization of the project results, ensuring that all necessary conditions for replicability and scaling of the proposed solutions are met.

This report, Deliverable 8.2 – Communication and Dissemination (C&D) Plan, is an integral part of WP8, being a handbook to accompany all the communication and dissemination activities carried out by the consortium towards various publics, stakeholders and end users. The plan outlines all the C&D activities foreseen during the project, detailing the C&D tools to be developed, laying out the key messages for Target Audiences and establishing the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to monitor the extent and impact of C&D efforts. This document constitutes the first version of the C&D Plan, which will be updated in Deliverable 8.4 Communication and Dissemination Plan V2 towards the end of the project.

1.3. Organisation of the Report

This document begins with an introduction to the concepts of Communication and Dissemination and explains the role each component has in maximizing the impact of the project and the uptake of its outputs. Next, it describes the Key Target Audiences who will be addressed and the Key Messages that will be directed towards them. Then, it describes the Tools and Channels used for each of the C&D components. Later, it outlines the Key Performance Indicators that will be used to track the impact of the C&D activities over time.

A critical part of this document covers Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Management of the key exploitable results produced. An outline plan is provided in the first version of this document, which will be expanded upon later in the project. This IPR management plan will feed into D8.5 Exploitation and Replication Plan, due in M42 (April 2028).

Finally, the document describes the rights and obligations of the project and its beneficiaries with respect to the commitment to the funding authorities.

2. Communication and Dissemination (C&D) Elements

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation are essential components to ensuring the impact of research outputs and results.

Communication deals with the flow of information about the project to a general or mixed audience, to inform society about the objectives, activities, and achievement of the project throughout its entire lifecycle, as well as with the flow of information within the project consortium.

Dissemination ensures that the results, new findings, and outputs of the project reach communities that need and can use them.

Exploitation deals with uptake, finding an end user for the results and products of the project, ensuring that the project has a practical application that can be used immediately by the stakeholders who need those resources and products.

In MOIRAI, a separate plan is foreseen for the exploitation of MOIRAI key exploitable results, by way of D8.5 Exploitation and Replication Plan, due in Month 42, i.e. in April 2028. This document, therefore, focuses on Communication and Dissemination elements alone.

The plan is implemented through addressing the following questions:

- **Who** are the target audiences for the MOIRAI specific outputs?
- **Why** is MOIRAI relevant to these audiences?
- **What** key messages does MOIRAI want to pass to these audiences?
- **How** can these messages be tailored to their target audiences?

Through this approach, we will identify the tools and channels that will be used to communicate the specific messages with the target audiences, to disseminate project results and to encourage their engagement.

Beneficiary institutions, participating SMEs and end users, and individuals involved in MOIRAI will act as promoters and interpreters of the project's results. From its very beginning the project will start sharing the aim, goals, the model framework information, preliminary results and any other project achievements. Carefully crafted messages delivered through suitable channels will publicize MOIRAI work. The purpose will be to generate demand for the data and products developed; encourage typical and non-typical data users to use and exploit the project's results. C&D activities also aim to draw the attention of national and regional governments and other public and private funding sources to the needs and benefits of research and innovation actions, and to attract the interest of supporting institutions. The final aim will be to enhance the reputation and visibility of MOIRAI at local, national and international levels.

2.1. Target Groups

MOIRAI aligns its approach with Horizon Europe, focusing on the Quintuple Helix, deemed as “highly relevant to the green transition (Carayannis et al. 2012¹) and

¹ Carayannis, E. G., Barth, T. D., & Campbell, D. F. (2012). The Quintuple Helix innovation model: global warming as a challenge and driver for innovation. *Journal of innovation and entrepreneurship*, 1, 1-12.

incorporating the “natural environment” as the fifth helix (Figure 2). This model for cooperation is thought to maximize innovation while focusing on the interests of the citizen. Thirteen specific target audiences were identified for MOIRAI under the sectors: Academia, Private Sector, Public Sector, and Civil Society.

Figure 2 - Quintuple Helix modified from Al-Ali et al. 2020².

A. Academia:

1. Coastal impact and risk experts
2. Global and regional ocean-climate modelling communities
3. Marine biologists and ecologist
4. Operational forecasting community

MOIRAI will bring ground-breaking evolutions on a multi-scale approach to climate predictions, bridging the various research communities previously listed and targeted. This can lead to further improvements and scale-up to higher TRLs of the solutions developed.

B. Private Sector:

5. Aquaculture farmers

² Al-Ali, F. A., Stephens, S. M., & Ajayan, T. S. (2020). Integration of the Quintuple Helix innovation Model into the Higher Education Sector: The case of Mohammed bin Rashid School of Government. *Integration*, 13(7).

6. Offshore renewable energies
7. Port activities
8. Ship operators
9. Multi-scale fisheries
10. Touristic sector

Local and specialised end-users of the blue economy are essential in promoting additional research and facilitating the widespread adoption of MOIRAI's innovations. The potential for future returns in terms of economic and environmental innovation will be presented so that they can integrate it into their management strategy (WP7). Intimate collaboration with the actors of the blue economy, will be engaged through the EUB (T8.4) providing feedback to the user-oriented hub REASSHORE (T6.5).

C. Public Sector:

1. Local and territorial decision-makers
2. EU and National public authorities

Local and national authorities are crucial for the further uptake of the innovations proposed. Policy recommendations and opportunities will be central and considered in the project's exploitation plan.

D. Civil Society

1. Coastal communities and NGOs

Acceptance and support by the wider population is also important to ensure the broad uptake of MOIRAI's solutions and technologies. Similar to public bodies and policymakers, the general public can influence the political debate and push for faster adoption of new and innovative science-based climate mitigation and adaptation strategies.

2.2. Key Messages

The following key messages will be transmitted through various media and communication channels throughout the project. The aim of defining key messages is to ensure that the messaging created is consistent and clear and in agreement with the project's goals, objectives and values. Additional key messages may be selected and adapted based on the specific communication needs, project timeline, relevant context

and circumstances. When part of a local communication plan, they will be adapted taking into consideration the local context, including language, and the internal institutional specifics, if applicable. The list below is a provisional and dynamic selection of current key messages from MOIRAI. The messages may be slightly amended or altered to a certain extent within the project without any fundamental change of the core meaning conveyed. New messages may also be added as the project matures and results become available.

MOIRAI Makes Ocean and Climate Forecasts More Accurate

MOIRAI is improving ocean models to better predict extreme events, coastal erosion, and long-term climate change. This helps communities stay prepared and resilient.

MOIRAI provides enhanced ocean-climate models:

MOIRAI **Optimizes Model Performance**: The optimization of MOIRAI's model suite will focus on efficient high-performance computing deployment, identification of performance bottlenecks, and adaptation of models to heterogeneous hardware.

MOIRAI performs **Comprehensive Model Testing**: Each improved regional ocean model will undergo rigorous testing, including extensive hindcast simulations, seasonal ensemble forecasts, and multidecadal projections.

MOIRAI performs **Model Calibration** for Marine Environments: Our project calibrates physical ocean models in the European Arctic Ocean, North Sea, and Mediterranean Sea, focusing on wave effects, inter-basin exchanges, shallow-water dynamics, and achieving higher resolution.

MOIRAI includes **Model Uncertainty Quantification**: We will quantify uncertainties through rigorous comparison of hindcast data with observations and assessments of inter-model discrepancies across various resolutions.

MOIRAI produces enhanced **climate projections**: We will improve ocean model forecasts by statistically downscaling (CMIP6) climate projections, implementing a two-step approach that includes re-gridding necessary variables and applying bias correction using reference datasets.

MOIRAI provides **Innovative Prediction Methodologies**: We will develop and replicate methodologies for seasonal to decadal predictions regarding coastal erosion and extreme events, integrating advanced models for improved climate change impact assessments.

MOIRAI includes a **Vulnerability and Resilience Framework (VFAR)**: Our framework will assess vulnerability and resilience through a structured process involving hazard identification, impact modelling, variable configuration, and contextual resilience quantification.

MOIRAI Supports a Healthier, More Sustainable Ocean

By enhancing our understanding of ocean health—from water quality to marine life—MOIRAI is supporting clean seas, sustainable seafood, and smart use of ocean resources like wind and aquaculture.

MOIRAI's Applications include:

MOIRAI provides **Coupled Model Insights for Aquaculture**: We will calibrate hydrodynamic-BGC models to provide critical insights into climate change impacts on mussels and the benefits of integrating offshore wind farms with multi-trophic aquaculture for sustainable resource management.

MOIRAI provides **Biogeochemical Advances**: We are enhancing biogeochemical modelling in coastal areas through collaborations, increasing resolution, and incorporating nutrient exchanges to better understand three regional seas: Arctic GRS, Mediterranean Sea, and North Sea.

MOIRAI performs **Ecosystem Resilience Assessments**: Our assessment of low-mid trophic ecosystems' resilience will include exploring sustainable management strategies for biodiversity and fisheries, utilizing marine ecosystem models alongside coupled hydrodynamic-BGC models.

MOIRAI Delivers Practical Tools for Coastal Protection

Through the digital hub REASSHORE, MOIRAI is creating early warning systems and easy-to-use indicators to help protect coasts and guide smart policies in the face of rising climate risks.

MOIRAI provides tools for managers and decision makers via a new hub called REASSHORE:

REASSHORE provides **indicators for Decision Makers**: We will design and select five complementary indicators across ocean state, socio-economic factors, and holistic measures to support actionable insights for decision-makers.

MOIRAI employs an **AI-Based Early Warning System**: An advanced early warning system will be developed, employing AI models to enhance prediction capabilities for extreme marine events like heat waves, surges, and flooding.

MOIRAI tests its methods and tools in the context of six use case areas, selected for providing coastal risk services (CR) or sustainable blue economy services (SBE):

1. Rethymno, Greece (CR)
2. Western Mediterranean (SBE)
3. North Sea – Western Denmark (CR)

4. North Sea Basin (SBE)
5. Disko Bay – Greenland (CR)
6. Greenland-Scotland Ridge (SBE)

3. Communication Tools and Activities

Communication activities will involve the use of mass media to share relevant information, raise awareness of the growing importance of ocean modelling for the purpose of understanding the ocean-climate nexus, and promote the project and its findings to various audiences, including groups beyond the project’s own community. The creation of a coherent image, messages adapted to the specific audiences and the translation of scientific results into layman terms by science communication and ocean literacy principles will enable the broadest possible outreach of the project.

Dedicated communication tools and activities for sharing MOIRAI information to the target audiences, have been established. A description of these communication tools and activities follows.

Figure 3 - The MOIRAI key visual is a seaside view of the prehistoric cemetery of the oldest submerged lost city of Pavlopetri in Laconia, Greece.

3.1. Branding

The first element in maximizing the visibility of MOIRAI is the development of a unique and distinctive visual identity, comprising a logo, look and style by which the project will come to be known. Although the project logo was developed at the time of presenting the proposal, the other visual elements were chosen later. Apart from the distinctive logo, a key image was selected to represent the project (Figure 3). The chosen image shows a seaside view of the prehistoric cemetery of the oldest submerged lost city of Pavlopetri in Laconia, Greece. Estimated to be about 5,000 years old, it is the oldest known city in the Mediterranean. This image was thought to be suitable for the project as it demonstrates some of the potential impacts of climate change as well as paying into the Greek theme of the project name and logo. Many visuals depicting climate change are very dark or violent, but this brighter photo rouses more positive emotions. This complete visual identity was delivered in January 2025, month 3 of the project, and consists of a logo (Figure 4), with versions for a variety of applications for different colour backgrounds and contexts, as well as lettering and a colour scheme (Figure 5).

Figure 4 - MOIRAI brand variations.

Figure 5 - MOIRAI brand elements.

3.2 Website

The public project website is ongoing and is due to be published in April 2025, at <https://moirai-project.eu/> (Figure 6). The website was established using the following criteria:

- Simple usability;
- Responsive web design;
- Clear and accessible structure;
- Appealing, accurate and updated content

The MOIRAI project website, together with social media, will be the main channel for online communication of the project. The MOIRAI website will be the go-to hub for information about project activities, news and achievements, collaborations, outputs and engagement opportunities. The website will be completely responsive, designed to function on multiple devices and on various operating systems.

Specifically, the website will provide the following initial information, which will be updated throughout the project lifetime to reflect the status of the project at any given time:

About: Objectives and Impacts; Partners; Management Structure; External Advisory Board; End Users.

Use Cases: Rethymno – Coastal Risk; Western Mediterranean – Blue Economy; North Sea – Coastal Risk; North Sea – Blue Economy; Greenland – Coastal Risk; Greenland-Scotland Ridge – Blue Economy.

Results: Deliverables, Publications, Training Materials; Communication Materials; Other Resources.

Applications: Impact Assessment; Risk and Damage Prediction; Vulnerability and Resilience Assessment Framework (VRAF); Model Optimization; Model Testing and Validation; Ocean-Climate Indicators; Early Warning System.

REASSHORE: About REASSHORE.

News: News, Press Releases.

MOIRAI

ABOUT ▾
USE CASES ▾
RESULTS ▾
APPLICATIONS ▾
REASSHORE ▾
NEWS & EVENTS ▾

OBJECTIVES

MOIRAI will greatly enhance our understanding and response to climate-related challenges

MOIRAI, named after the three Greek goddesses of fate, stands as a pioneering project at the intersection of past, present, and future. MOIRAI weaves a comprehensive understanding of the ocean's dynamics and biogeochemical cycles through advanced models, integrating historical data, current observations, and future projections. Integrated into the frameworks of Destination Earth (DE) and the European Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO), MOIRAI will significantly advance our comprehension and mitigation of climate-related challenges.

02/13/2025 EVENTS

7th European Climate Change Adaptation Conference

02/03/2025 NEWS

MOIRAI at SEACLIM Kick Off

01/31/2025 NEWS

Driving Change with the Launch of MOIRAI!

Newsletter

Name

Email

Affiliation

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Figure 6 - MOIRAI website homepage.

To increase the audience visiting the MOIRAI project website, partners' and collaborators' websites will cross-post content, e.g. News from MOIRAI, and encourage their audiences to visit the MOIRAI project website. An example of how partners' and collaborators' websites (EurOcean) can be used to promote the project is shown in Figure 7. Partner and project websites will also encourage visits to the MOIRAI social media pages.

Figure 7 - Partner websites can and should be used to promote MOIRAI.

3.3. Social Media

Social media accounts have been created for MOIRAI on Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube (Figure 8). Links with other relevant projects and initiatives have been established and will continue to be updated throughout the lifetime of MOIRAI. Each of these platforms offers access to a different form of content as well as a different type of user. Twitter, for example, is a fast-paced platform that provides up to the minute information on trending topics. It is widely used by many of MOIRAI's target audiences (see below) and is also a source of information regularly used by journalists and the popular media, influencers and leaders; therefore, Twitter will be the main channel used for MOIRAI communication and dissemination. For all social media channels, the official MOIRAI hashtag is **#MOIRAI**.

Figure 8 - MOIRAI social media channels.

3.4. Brochure/Pamphlet

A digital brochure will be created during the first months of the project. It will serve as a basis on which the rest of the communication material within the project will be created. A first draft of the brochure, which is currently under development, is shown in Figure 9. The characteristics will be that it is:

- highly optimisable for various digital mediums including the web,
- easily customizable to serve each partner's needs,
- easily sharable across various social media channels,
- multi-screen compatible.

Online communication tools will also be uploaded on the website (see Section 3.2), distributed via social media channels (see Section 3.3) and distributed over partner's networks.

Figure 9 - First look at MOIRAI brochure (under development).

3.5. Templates

The project’s general templates have been designed based on the standards and rules set out within the project’s branding. As well as establishing uniformity and consistency, they also convey the common project visual identity. All project communication and management templates are available under the project’s file sharing system.

PowerPoint Template

The standard PowerPoint template is shown in Figure 10. The template is a partially animated, modern presentation with dynamic slides and smooth transitions that can be adapted to any project-related presentation scenario.

Figure 10 - MOIRAI PowerPoint Template.

Deliverables Template

The standard Deliverable template (Figure 11) was designed for use by the consortium. The template includes layouts and formatting that will be common to all deliverables, as well as standardized cover pages. The deliverable template includes recognition of the relevant contributions of consortium members to the development of the deliverable, and acknowledgement of financial support through the Horizon Europe Programme.

Figure 11 - MOIRAI Deliverables Template (sample pages).

4 Dissemination Tools and Activities

Although communication channels can and will be used to disseminate the project results, there is a collection of tools specifically designed to support dissemination at the broadest possible scale. These results-oriented channels are described in this section.

4.1 Peer-Reviewed Publications

Peer-reviewed publications in reputable and high impact journals will be one of the central channels for reaching the research and ocean science communities. Thereby the results of the project will benefit from professional approval of scientific experts and from the long-term availability provided by the archiving systems of these journals. In line with the EC requirements, peer-reviewed publications will be open and accessible to anyone, i.e., published via gold (no embargo) or green (self-archived) open access.

Target journals for the results of MOIRAI include but are not limited to:

- Arctic Journal,
- Biogeosciences;
- Data Intelligence,

- Ecological Modelling;
- Environmental Reviews,
- Frontiers for Young Minds,
- Frontiers in Earth Science,
- Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution, Geoscientific
- Frontiers in Marine Science,
- Journal of Geophysical Research;
- Journal of Marine Science and Engineering,
- Journal of Open-Source Software,
- Marine Technology Society Journal,
- Methods in Ecology and Evolution,
- Model Development,
- Nature Scientific Data,
- Nature,
- Polar Science,
- Science.

4.2 Scientific Conferences

Where possible, MOIRAI results will be presented at European scientific meetings and conferences, and the results published in the proceedings of those events. Potential meetings and conferences for this project are listed below.

- Arctic Circle,
- Arctic Frontiers,
- Arctic Science Summit Week (ASSW),
- EuroGOOS International Conferences,
- European Geophysical Union (EGU),
- GEO events,
- International Council for Exploration of the Sea (ICES) Annual Science Conference,

- International Symposium on the Effects of Climate Change on the World’s Ocean (ECCWO),
- Ocean Science Meetings (OSM),
- Oceanology International,
- OCEANS conferences,
- UN Ocean conferences.

4.3 Organisation of Dedicated Events

The MOIRAI work plan includes the organization of a number of dedicated events, meaning events organized by the consortium members. These include:

- Seven workshops with members of the External Advisory Board (T1.5);
- Eight online webinars or seminars with the End Users Board ensuring feedback and laying the ground for replication and upscaling (T8.4);
- One workshop with relevant decision-makers to inform and train them on the science-to-policy interface of REASSHORE (T8.3, M40);
- Focus groups and surveys with local stakeholders for each use case (T7.1);
- Co-organized digital or physical events with connected projects (T8.2).

These events will secure continuous and targeted dissemination of the project's results to all relevant stakeholders and target groups.

4.4 Selected Contact Lists and Websites:

Updates and press releases about important milestones in the project and marked achievements will be sent to a selection of distribution lists and dedicated websites. These include, Research*EU Results (CORDIS), Oceanbuzz, Marine and Oceans, Sea Technology, and more.

4.5 Technical Reports, Popular Science Articles, and Policy Briefs

MOIRAI foresees the development of catalogues and reports, securing access to information concerning knowledge and innovation development that is particularly relevant for all the blue economy players will be developed.

The MOIRAI team aims to publish at least five popular science articles, promoted by the different project partners, will be published in non-academic magazines, selected branch media, journals, and blogs, and all media relevant to key target groups (e.g. Horizon Magazine, Eco Magazine). These articles will target investors, industry players, technology providers, policymakers, social platforms, but also the general public. Partners will also promote their own publications at the national level.

At least one policy brief will be developed concerning the key performance indicators on coastal resilience and the use of the science-to-policy REASSHORE interface to achieve targets and analyse scenarios (D8.3).

4.6 Deliverables and Other Digital Resources

Project deliverables, training material, and other digital resources will be made available through the MOIRAI Zenodo community³, to guarantee their long-term preservation. Common search engines such as Google Scholar and Microsoft Research are harvesting metadata for assets hosted at Zenodo and provide high visibility. The consortium will make available information relating to methods and tools with test datasets, and open reports produced within the project through the MOIRAI Zenodo Community.

5. Exploitation Tools and Activities

Exploitation in MOIRAI is strongly linked to Stakeholder engagement as these stakeholders will use the MOIRAI results beyond the lifetime of the project. The initial Exploitation and Replication Plan (E&R plan) will be delivered at M6 (April 2025) and revised at M24 (October 2026). Following a step-by-step methodology, it will provide a roadmap for the exploitation of MOIRAI results to higher TRLs, up to operationalisation. A list of Preliminary Key Exploitable Results (KER) with the potential exploitation pathways has been defined below considering the innovative products and tools generated by the project (Table 1). This includes the partner owner of the results. A representative from each partner institution will monitor all generated project results and be characterised as either commercially exploitable or free for dissemination. Support services from the Horizon Results Booster will also be assessed to maximize the project result exploitation opportunities. For MOIRAI, a roadmap will be defined during the project to ensure its legacy.

³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/moirai>

Individual partner exploitation plans: Each partner has already a clear exploitation strategy to turn the project activities into concrete scientific and/or economic values and impact on society.

Table 1 - Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and their Key Impact Pathways (KIPs). Target groups as per Section 2.1.

Key Exploitable Result	Key Impact Pathway	Target Groups	Type of Impact
Downscaled climate models	1. Creating high-quality new knowledge; 3. Fostering diffusion of knowledge and Open source; 9. Leveraging investment in R&I	A1-A2-A4	Scientific Economic Technological
Refined regional ocean physics models	1. Creating high-quality new knowledge; 2. Strengthening human capital in R&I; 4. Addressing EU policy priorities and global challenges through R&I; 5. Delivering benefits and impact through R&I missions; 6. Strengthening the uptake of research and innovation in society; 9. Leveraging investment in R&I	A1-A2-A4 B C1 D	Scientific Societal Economic Technological
Refined regional BGC models	1. Creating high-quality new knowledge; 2. Strengthening human capital in R&I; 4. Addressing EU policy priorities and global challenges through R&I; 5. Delivering benefits and impact through R&I;	A B C1 D	Scientific Societal Economic Technological

Key Exploitable Result	Key Impact Pathway	Target Groups	Type of Impact
	6. Strengthening the uptake of research and innovation in society; 9. Leveraging investment in R&I		
Novel multi-scale Marine Ecosystem Models (MEMs) parametrization	1. Creating high-quality new knowledge; 3. Fostering diffusion of knowledge and Open source; 4. Addressing EU policy priorities and global challenges through R&I; 5. Delivering benefits and impact through R&I missions; 8. Creating more and better jobs; 9. Leveraging investment in R&I	A1-A2-A3 B5 C D	Scientific Societal Economic Technological
Mid-low trophic fisheries and aquaculture model	1. Creating high-quality new knowledge; 2. Strengthening human capital in R&I; 4. Addressing EU policy priorities and global challenges through R&I; 5. Delivering benefits and impact through R&I; 6. Strengthening the uptake of R&I in society; 7. Generating innovation-based growth; 8. Creating more and better jobs; 9. Leveraging investment in R&I	A1-A2-A3 B1-B2-B5 C D	Scientific Societal Economic Technological

Key Exploitable Result	Key Impact Pathway	Target Groups	Type of Impact
High-fidelity coastal models	1. Creating high-quality new knowledge; 3. Fostering diffusion of knowledge and Open source;	A1-A2-A4	Scientific
Coastal risk and impact models	1. Creating high-quality new knowledge; 3. Fostering diffusion of knowledge and Open source; 4. Addressing EU policy priorities and global challenges through R&I; 5. Delivering benefits and impact through R&I missions; 6. Strengthening the uptake of research and innovation in society; 9. Leveraging investment in R&I	A B C D	Scientific Societal Economic Technological
Community vulnerability & resilience frameworks	1. Creating high-quality new knowledge; 3. Fostering diffusion of knowledge and Open source; 4. Addressing EU policy priorities and global challenges through R&I; 5. Delivering benefits and impact R&I missions; 6. Strengthening the uptake of R&I in society;	A1-A2-A3 B C D	Scientific Societal Economic Technological

Key Exploitable Result	Key Impact Pathway	Target Groups	Type of Impact
	8. Creating more and better jobs; 9. Leveraging investment in R&I		
Complementary ocean state and holistic indicators	1. Creating high-quality new knowledge; 2. Strengthening human capital in R&I; 3. Fostering diffusion of knowledge and Open source; 4. Addressing EU policy priorities and global challenges through R&I; 6. Strengthening the uptake of R&I in society;	A B C D	Scientific Societal
REASSHORE	1. Creating high-quality new knowledge; 2. Strengthening human capital in R&I 3. Fostering diffusion of knowledge and Open source; 4. Addressing EU policy priorities and global challenges R&I; 5. Delivering benefits and impact through R&I missions; 6. Strengthening the uptake of R&I in society; 7. Generating innovation-based growth; 8. Creating more and better jobs; 9. Leveraging investment in R&I	A1-A2-A3 B C D	Scientific Societal Economic Technological

5.1. Stakeholder Engagement

Stakeholder engagement is central to MOIRAI, with the development of ambitious solutions for environmental and resource management depending on the involvement of various stakeholder including coastal and environmental managers, ocean-climate modelling communities, marine biologists and ecologists, forecasting community, offshore industries, port managers, ship operators, tourism sector, decision makers, public authorities, and native communities.

Policy-makers engagement will be guaranteed via a workshop training on REASSHORE (WP8??). The WPs are strategically designed to ensure close collaboration among the involved partners.

To this end, MOIRAI has dedicated several tasks to stakeholder engagement, including Interdisciplinary scientific engagement and synergies (T8.2) and Communication with policymakers and recommendations (T8.3). These tasks aim to share and promote the results of MOIRAI, and to work together with other projects, communities, initiatives, and decision makers to bring greater relevance to project results. Stakeholders will be engaged through the dissemination channels described in Section 4, which include events, conferences, as well as collaboration through clusters or working groups, and through joint ventures including special sessions at conferences, joint publication of special issues of peer-reviewed journals.

On the policy side, T8.2 will seek to engage in a sustained dialogue for recommendations and identification of policy targets in the framework of European climate mitigation and adaptation strategies. A dedicated Science-to-Policy workshop is scheduled for M40 (February 2028) to train available stakeholders to interact with REASSHORE interface and use it to elaborate strategies to increase coastal resilience.

5.3 Barriers to Optimal Exploitation

The consortium has identified a series of potential barriers that could hamper the exploitation of the project results. These are summarised below:

Low replicability due to resource unavailability: MOIRAI solutions can be applied and adjusted according to the end users' needs and the available resources. Data streams (outside the ones included in the project) will be identified.

Funding is needed to scale up technologies: The exploitation plan will support the further uptake of the expected TRL5 proposal, by outlining strategies, and investment opportunities.

Lack of authorities and policy-makers engagement in adoptions MOIRAI's solutions:

MOIRAI is working together with policymakers to ensure their engagement and a path towards oriented future funding for the upscale of MOIRAI's solutions at European and global level. Furthermore, five members of the consortium are national entities who will work on incorporating the results nationally.

Low replicability due to end user incompatibility: MOIRAI will offer various solutions and end-users can choose the best one based on their needs, plans, and project data. Project innovations are outdated by new discoveries: The project will monitor the research landscape during and beyond the project, understand discoveries, and adjust the innovation trajectory to meet its needs.

6. C&D Management and Reporting

The continuous reporting of dissemination is a specific tool for monitoring partners' dissemination activity during the whole project. The reporting is carried out by each partner using an excel sheet template that will be provided by WP8 leaders. The excel sheet will be hosted by the coordinator (NTUA) on the project's file sharing area and will contain the required input for continuous reporting.

The continuous reporting of communication activities will enable monitoring and evaluation of the impact of the project and will provide guidance for modification or redefinition of the C&D plan, if needed.

Partners will be asked to report every 3 months communication and dissemination activities they have performed. To facilitate accurate monitoring and assessment of the dissemination and communication activities, and to understand the impact of the actions carried out, all partners must register the activities that they implement and save evidence of the activities conducted (e.g. agenda/programme, participant list, photos, recording), with all evidentiary materials complying strictly with GDPR requirements.

Monitoring and tracking of website and social media usage, reach and engagement will be managed through Google Analytics (website) and social media integral monitoring tools (e.g., Twitter Analytics, LinkedIn Analytics). The results of C&D monitoring will be included in the regular reporting cycle under WP8.

6.1 Key Performance Indicators and Impact

Performance of the dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities will be monitored over the entire lifetime of the project. Information and data to support performance evaluation will be gathered through the continuous reporting provided by

the partners. This continuous reporting will enable monitoring and evaluation of the impact of the project and will provide guidance for modification or redefinition of the C&D plan, if needed.

Monitoring of dissemination impacts will be carried out using existing trackers e.g., number of reads, number of followers, number of citations, for peer-reviewed publications, as provided by the publishers and by other platforms such as Research Gate, ISI Web of Knowledge, Scopus, or similar. Information such as “number of participants” at conference sessions, workshops and other dissemination events, will also be collected whenever possible.

For activities in support of exploitation, efforts will be made to assess the impact of the activity by performing a pre- and post-analysis of the knowledge, attitudes and understanding of the participants. Table 2 provides a summary of the performance indicators (KPIs) that will be used for MOIRAI communication and dissemination activities.

Table 2 - Key Performance Indicators for Communication and Dissemination.

Channel	KPIs
Project Website:	Website online, ≥ 30 news accumulated over 4 years. ≥ 5,000 visits by year 3.
Social media:	≥ 200 posts accumulated over 4 years. ≥ 500 followers per social media platform.
Digital and Media Channels:	≥ 4 communication campaigns. ≥ 16 newsletters. ≥ 4 press releases.
Partners' Channels and Networks:	> 50 channels redirecting to the project's website.
EC's Media Channels:	> 4 dedicated publications.

7. Intellectual Property Rights Management

The management of Intellectual Property (IP) rights has been established according to the Consortium Agreement (CA) endorsed by all partners. The consortium has created a robust strategy for handling IP, designed to balance the sharing of results with the preservation of each consortium partner's IP rights. This approach guarantees effective

execution of communication and dissemination tasks without impeding entities from safeguarding their respective IPs.

Detailed instructions for managing Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) will be clearly laid out in the Project Handbook. The consortium's approach to IPRs will adhere to the guiding principles set in the CA. Recognizing the ownership of background IP by individual partners, the resulting foreground IP born from the project will be attributed to the generating participant. In cases where the emergence of foreground IP is a collaborative effort (where distinct components of a result cannot be attributed to specific participants), joint ownership will be the default, unless divergent consensus is reached. Access to background IP, necessary for project implementation, will be provided without charging royalties, unless there's unanimous consent among participants to deviate from this arrangement (for instance, a participant might restrict or limit background IP access).

For project implementation, access to foreground IP is granted to consortium members without royalty obligations. In the event of disputes between partners, the consortium has opted for collaborative dispute resolution mechanisms — encompassing mediation, arbitration, expert determination, or a combination of these approaches— mitigating the complexities and expenses of legal proceedings. Any restriction affecting access rights of other partners due to such disputes must be communicated to them. The Results Ownership List (ROL) will be prepared in the final reporting period detailing the final owners (single or multiple) of IP after the project is over.

8. Rights and Obligations for C&D

8.1. Obligation and Right to use the EU Emblem

Acknowledgment of the EU funding is an obligation (article II.8 of General Conditions). The EU emblem is the single most important visual brand used to acknowledge the origin and ensure the visibility of EU funding. Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be created or used to highlight EU support, unless previously agreed with the European Commission.

Any dissemination of results should display the EU emblem (Figure 12) accompanied by a funding statement (Funded by the European Union') mentioning the EU's support. Both the EU emblem and the funding statement are essential to acknowledge EU support. As a rule, they always go hand in hand and must not be separated.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Figure 12 - EU emblem and funding statement.

Partners wishing to include a general statement about the EU in a written communication, may use the following standard general statement:

“The Member States of the European Union have decided to link together their know-how, resources and destinies. Together, they have built a zone of stability, democracy and sustainable development whilst maintaining cultural diversity, tolerance and individual freedoms. The European Union is committed to sharing its achievements and its values with countries and peoples beyond its borders.”

To provide further information on EU institutions and policies, internet links in publications produced by implementing partners must refer to official EU sources, in particular <http://europa.eu> and/or the relevant EU Delegation website.

4.2 Obligation to Keep Track of Results

Partners must keep track of all their dissemination and communication activities, all of which should be reported by each partner at EC reporting stages. Partners are required to report any publication and dissemination activities on the template provided by NTUA on a quarterly basis. These reports contain information on activities carried out during the past quarter as well as activities foreseen in the coming quarter. Partners are encouraged to take photos of communication and dissemination activities in which they take part. Abstracts, posters, presentations, links, and other relevant material related to these activities should be provided along with the quarterly report. For further information, please refer to Section 6.

9. Concluding Remarks

MOIRAI has outlined a comprehensive C&D plan, providing guidelines for communication and dissemination to different audiences and through different channels. These guidelines are designed to support all other work packages in the project by providing a set of visually appealing tools with consistent look and feel that can help build confidence in MOIRAI and its messaging. The C&D plan is particularly relevant to WP7 and WP8, where extensive contact with stakeholders takes place.

This document will be updated and improved throughout the lifetime of the MOIRAI project.

MOIRAI

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